

X Interview ICORSAKey:

I: Interviewer
R: Respondent

I: **There's a small introduction, which was included in the email. Since you have signed the consent form already, I am going to skip this due to time limitations. I hope that's okay?**

R: Yes.

I: **Okay, great. So first I am interested to get to know more about your role in [X] a little bit better, so I would say first we start with your personal role in the network.**

R: Sure. So do you want me to address it?

I: **Yes, please. So what is your position within the network structure and what makes your position special?**

R: [X] is an initiative that we are managing at the European Schoolnet. We are a network of 34 ministries of education. [X] has been running for nine years and we have been managing it, at the beginning on behalf of the commission and after three years by ourselves. We are funded by the commission but not a service contract anymore. My position within European Schoolnet is that I am the Science Programme Manager, so I am in charge of making sure that all the science projects, science technology, engineering, and mathematics projects that we run work together. In particular, in [X] I have been the project manager from day one. So I basically was coordinating from the moment we got the grant until now.

I: **That's great. How did you join the network and how long have you been part of the network? I guess this is nine years since the beginning?**

R: Exactly. So it's clear it was actually a call from DG Research DG Research and Innovation, so they were looking to create a platform that would ensure that all the materials and projects that were funded by the commission had in place anything that had to do with STEM education, so because one of the problems that whenever a project finishes all of the materials disappear. So the DG Research wanted to make sure that there was a place where everything they had been funding was still there and accessible for teachers and other stakeholders in STEM education, so that's why they lodged the call. So we applied for it and became the service provider. Then it's continued to be funded since then through the different grants and basically that's how we got into it and myself as manager.

I: **Do you know all the other members of the network? So do you see each other or exchange frequently?**

R: Just so it's clear, it's a network in the sense that we have a community set up under [X] but we are the only coordinator. So we don't have official partners. What we have is we set up a community where we have different stakeholders, including ministries, organisations in STEM education, and

teachers working on it. So we work with them slightly different. So we have (unclear 00:02:52) working group where we have 22 ministries providing advice and guidance and recommendations of what should be the actions on STEM education, so we meet them about two or three times a year.

We have [X] ambassadors who are teachers that work on a voluntary basis and are selected through a very rigorous process, and not easy, and we have about 500 of them working around Europe promoting and supporting STEM education, following some [X] guidelines, and we have different organisations who are supporting [X] on STEM education either through collaborations or specific campaigns. While the ministries, as I say, we would see two or three times a year, the teachers we obviously cannot finance seeing them, all 500, so what we do is we bring the most active ones to specific events in Brussels and other events and for the other organisations we organise different events like [X] Projects Networking events where we (unclear 00:03:56) with those interested and discuss specific topics.

I: Great. So do you think it is important to know each other to build trust?

R: I think it's important to know each other. That doesn't mean that you actually need to meet physically but there is a trust that works from working together and knowing that you have a common goal, for sure.

I: Definitely. Okay, so now we are moving to the part where we would like to talk about the background of the community and the context. So what was the context of emergence, when and why has [X] been launched and what has been changing in the past nine years?

R: It was launched originally with a limited scope of making sure that all the materials that were created in public-funded projects did not disappear once the funding for the projects ran out, but it has developed into a community where while it has a portal, the portal is no longer the priority, the priority is the exchange between the different stakeholders on STEM education.

I: What do you think has been changing?

R: In terms of [X] or the project?

I: In terms of [X] and I think how the project has been going?

R: The main differences are the first few years of course we had – to give you a very basic example we had to go around telling people, “Here is [X]. Are you sure you don't want to upload your materials? We'll do it for you,” to a situation where we don't have to look for it, the projects know about it or they come and provide the resources and they know that we are providing a service to all these projects. We also know that, for example, for key events, having [X] means that you are going to get a broader perspective on STEM education and it's a very good way of getting support for your initiatives and your actions.

I: What are the activities to work towards the objective? You mentioned some of the science networking events and you bring teachers to Brussels. Is there a clear role division between your team or division of labour? Who is doing what in the project?

- R: It's quite a different initiative. We only have one partner, I would say, so we need to coordinate the whole thing, but we have very clear support from ministries and teachers in the different actions, so they are pretty much aware of how they can support [X].
- I: **Okay. I would like to move now to the structure and the format of the [X] community. So we would like to find out why your community has the form that it has. So we would like to talk about the network model here. So could you describe to me the structure of [X]?**
- R: The structure is actually defined by the contractual limitation with DG Research. We have a contract where we only have one organisation as a partner, as I was saying, so European Schoolnet is the sole direct beneficiary of the contract, and then we provide financing, for example, to ministries and other STEM organisations based on third-party agreements, and in that sense we are completely responsible for financial reporting on their behalf as well.
- I: **As the legal character, do you think you can call this community a company or an association?**
- R: Not at all. This is just a project. From a legal perspective, this is a project, that's it.
- I: **As a formalisation website, chat room, regular meetings?**
- R: We do have the [X] community. We do have management tools for the ministries and the teachers. Yes, we have online tools for that.
- I: **You also have regular meetings where you bring teachers to Brussels and you have network events?**
- R: Correct. We cannot bring all of them. We have 500 so we can only bring 30 from time to time.
- I: **What has been changed meanwhile and why, key moments and decisions? We would like to find out how did the structure of [X] develop and what was the thinking behind it?**
- R: The original [X] was just us, just European Schoolnet coordinating from [X] 2. So the numbers represent the contract we had with the commission. So after three years, it got expanded to also have national contact points, so organisations that acted on behalf of [X] at a national level, and in [X] 3 we expanded to having the ministries and a wider teacher's network. So you can see the expansion in terms of people involved with key responsibilities.
- I: **Great. Do you know who decided to choose this expansion after three years?**
- R: Yes. It was a combination of the commission and us and European Schoolnet. It was a way of supporting STEM education better.
- I: **When you think of [X], can you give any pros and cons of this specific model based on your experience? So regarding aims, membership, funding, and geographic spread?**

R: I guess the only difficult aspect is the financing regarding third parties. So, for example, we have a budget of €15,000 for national contact points, but for that €15,000, which is not that much money for many countries, we actually have a very complicated reporting procedure, which is established by the commission to ensure eligibility, so that means every single flight you need a boarding pass, every meeting you need timesheets, every single event you need a lot of proof that, for just a small amount of money, it becomes a burden for many organisations.

I: **Diversity and gender are frequently discussed topics, as you may hear. So for [X], would you say it plays a role for example implementation of specific structures or policies, parity in decision-making, decision-making bodies or positions, or do you have any formal or informal mechanisms for gender and diversity dynamics?**

R: In terms of the management of [X]?

I: **Management and inclusion of the partners.**

R: We do not have an active policy. We strive for gender neutralities. We do not pay attention to that. I have to say it's heavily female-biased but that's just in terms of colleagues applying for jobs. It also happens in terms of [X] teachers but we also know that women are overpopulating teaching positions, so it kind of happens naturally.

I: **Now I would like to speak a little bit more about the members of [X], or we can say partners or teachers or ministries. We would like to find out about the membership model. So regarding the membership model, can you describe in detail are they becoming a member of this community or are they applying?**

R: Any teacher or any organisation that wants to be part of [X], they are just by the fact of using [X] services, be it the portal, the events, the campaigns. So, for example, we just had a STEM Discovery Week organised where we had over 4,700 schools, so for us, that means there was a schools part of the [X] community. That's completely open and we have teachers from across the world, not only in Europe, being part of it. Now there is a second-tier for teachers where they want to become a [X] ambassador. To become a [X] ambassador, we run courses and we have organised three so far in the last three years. We receive applications. We can only take 300 people into the course. Last time we got over 3,000 applications, so you have an idea. Then we select the 300 who then do the course. This is a two-month online course on many things about [X] and STEM education.

By the time they have finished, only if they've got a rating of over 60% are they eligible to apply to become a [X] ambassador. Once they apply, they still need to be approved by the ministry of education of each country. In the end, if you imagine these 500 ambassadors that we have, those have gone through the whole process and then they do get the [X] title, which is actually not for life, it actually gets renewed every year based on the work they have done. So they can either resign afterwards or we can actually say that we cannot renew it based on their performance. So it is quite a highly-sought and difficult title to achieve. In terms of ministries, so the Ministry of Education can apply to become part of the (unclear 00:14:06) working groups, so that's a bit easier for ministries, and then for national contact points, as you know

other organisations, there was a call for organisations and we could only select a few countries.

I: Great. In your opinion, why do you think members are choosing to join the network? This could be teachers or schools, why are they participating? Are there any incentives?

R: Well, if you care about science education then the best way to work is with others, and [X] provides that network where you can actually find materials, collaborate, and all depending on where your interests are.

I: So now we would like to talk a little bit about the network funding model. So more questions on more concrete managerial issues in particular how the governance or management of [X] is structured, but also the funding sources that you employ. Can you please tell me which sources do you utilise for funding? So for membership, project funding, national grants, SME-based, consultancy?

R: We have a grant from the DG for Research and Innovation, so from the Horizon 2020 programme. Additionally, we co-fund both the ministry, the national contact points and European Schoolnet co-funds a number of activities in different ways, collaborating with other projects, through (unclear 00:15:35) ministries membership, with industry, but about I would say two-thirds of the budget is from DG Research directly.

I: So from Horizon 2020?

R: Yes.

I: Do you know if there is an annual budget?

R: Of course there is an annual budget. We have a contract.

I: There's a contract and there is an annual budget, of course. Is there any longer-term budget projections?

R: The third contract we have is until September and we have been informed that there should be another grant starting in 2020 for another three years.

I: How important is the funding? How much resources are dedicated in [X] to secure funding?

R: Funding is significantly important. We actually do need to work quite a bit towards it. I couldn't be able to measure it but it is something we need to constantly be aware of.

I: A little bit more questions on the governance and management structure again. Can you please tell me in detail again who has the managing responsibilities in [X], board of directors, executive committee, advisory board?

R: In the first instance it's myself as project manager, but of course I answer to European Schoolnet in terms of direction, so it needs to feed not only the STEM agenda but European Schoolnet's general agenda, and on the other

side the European Commission has DG Research as their main funder of the initiative.

I: Do you also have a principal committee member board, chair, co-chair, vice-chair?

R: No.

I: Regarding communication, do you have regular management meetings and how frequent?

R: We do have meetings with the commission. We have project management meetings internally but that's in-house so that's with my team at European Schoolnet.

I: How do you measure and monitor the effectiveness of [X]?

R: We also have an evaluation and it's carried out by the Manchester Metropolitan University as an external evaluator.

I: Does [X] have a five-year road map?

R: We have three-year road maps, which is the contractual duration of our work basically.

I: Is it publicly available?

R: The description of work? I don't know.

I: It will be great for us to retrieve it if there is one publicly available.

R: I don't think there's a public version because that's a contract with the commission and contracts with the commission are not usually public. You can definitely see the terms of reference.

I: We are progressing very quickly. Do you have a plan to foresee any risks and identify actions to prevent them? I am asking if you have a risk and mitigation plan.

R: Yes, every project at European Schoolnet has one.

I: A governance issue is often the distribution of information and knowledge as a main driver for people to be a part of a community. So can you please describe how information is made available and circulated among members or partners?

R: That's changed throughout the years, but we have first direct communications through the [X] newsletters and digest and social media, but because we are a network of ministries of education we also have ministries sharing all the information from [X] to their teachers, to give you an example.

I: So if ministries are sharing that can we say all the members are receiving the same information?

- R: All the ministries are getting the same information. How or what they choose to share with their teachers or their countries depends on the ministry, I would say, because it might depend on priorities for the country.
- I: **What would you say which general issues affect the effect governance? What is needed for good management? For instance, the trust issues between director, how this trust is established and maintained, which challenges are faced due to cultural differences between management board? Do you think there are any conflicts with members of the networks or their affiliations or maybe the schools or the teachers?**
- R: This is not just about this project but projects in general. You just need to understand that every organisation or person has different priorities and you should always try to understand what they need in order to supply their need. Don't just try to sell your product regardless of who you are talking to.
- I: **Definitely. Okay, so challenges and problems with the network, what is really interesting for us and our ambition to construct a global network for RRING is in fact where the potential challenges or difficulties lie. Hence I would like to go a little bit into those challenges, so what kind of problems did [X] face? Do you know something about that? For example, potential difficulties could be were there any cases where the network members, maybe some of the schools, have dropped out?**
- R: No. We haven't had that. If you are looking for recommendations to set up a network, my comment would be mostly to not try to force people to come to you, in the sense that if you set up a platform where to be a member you need to login, you need to work in our platform, you need to follow our instructions, that's going to be a lot tougher. You need to go to where people are, so that means having a plan where you will be reaching people's inboxes, where you will be letting them work on whatever network they want, so be it Facebook, Twitter, or any other social media platforms. Some people really don't care about the online communications, so you're going to have to have face to face actions. Others only care about online so you need the presence there, and always have a wide variety of messages so you target all of the different audiences.
- I: **Definitely. Are there any conflicts with members of the networks and their affiliation to an organisation? For example, when the organisation's objectives are not in line with the objective of [X]?**
- R: No we don't because we don't have one answer that fits everybody. We are very aware that it depends on the ministry and the school. So it is more of an open market where they can choose the parts that fit them. We are never trying to fit everything for everybody.
- I: **If you could warn us about any potential pitfalls, what would it be? Is there anything general or specific that we should be aware of when we want to establish our network?**
- R: Just make sure that you don't design something that is so rigid that only if they follow everything they can join. Make it more open to different ways of working and different priorities.

I: So flexible to fit everybody. Great. That's it. We went through all of the questions. That was very quick; it was only about 24 minutes, so thank you very much for such an efficient and effective interview. Thank you very much for sharing your experience and in particular taking time for this interview.

R: No problem.

I: I don't know if there's anything we didn't speak about or any other issues that you would like to raise?

R: No. I am just looking forward to seeing how you use this information and how you design your network.

I: As this interview is recorded, you can receive the recording if you would like to, and we can share the results with you once we collect all the interview data and process them.

R: Excellent. I would be happy. I don't need the interview, but it would be interesting to see how you are actually using it.

I: Okay, great. We will be in touch. Thank you very much for your time.

R: No problem.

I: Have a good day. Goodbye.

R: Bye.

(End of recording)